

Title

Challenges and recommendations for research security: Learning from research ethics and integrity.

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Abstract

Collaborative and open research combined with influential technological advancements and geopolitical tensions allow Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) to become prone to Research Security (RS) risks. Despite its recent conceptualization, RS has been swiftly recognised as a critical issue globally. Building upon existing guidance, it is necessary to adopt policy actions relatively quickly without creating new structures and by avoiding excessive procedural compliance.

To this direction, the CHANGER consortium recommends the following policy actions integrating RS considerations with research culture of ethics and integrity, to build resilience to RS risks while ensuring freedom and openness of research :

Policy recommendation 1: Establish a common understanding and promote RS as a shared responsibility within the research ecosystem.

Policy recommendation 2: Leverage existing institutional procedures e.g. by adapting training programs on research ethics and integrity programs, to embed RS considerations in the research culture.

Policy recommendation 3: Cultivate professional expertise in RS for specialists to act as advisors.

Policy recommendation 4: Support capacity building through the development of new approaches and new tools to assess and manage RS risks.

Concluding remarks. Leveraging experience and insights from research ethics and integrity infrastructure offers valuable opportunities to raise awareness and establish procedures for safeguarding RS. The proposed policy actions offer flexibility to meet specific research needs of each HEI and RPO, and are proportionate to related risks rising from each research project. They respect the autonomy of HEIs and RPOs and protect freedom of research. By fostering capacity-building for researchers and cultivating a culture of awareness, shared responsibility, and proactive responsiveness, the responsible internationalisation of research can be effectively realised.

Graphical Abstract

Keywords

research security; policy; research ethics; research integrity.

1. Problem Identification

International, interdisciplinary and open research has been promoted for decades by research funding organisations, due to its significant value in accelerating scientific knowledge and global innovation. However, the landscape of international research is changing due to rising geopolitical tensions, foreign interference and the use of influential technological advancements for strategic, geopolitical, or economic objectives.¹ In support of this, the European Commission (EC) has identified Artificial Intelligence technologies, Quantum technologies and Biotechnologies as 3 out of 4 critical technology areas with the highest likelihood of presenting the most sensitive and immediate risk related to technology security and technology leakage.² These three technologies are extensive and intensive areas of research for Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) at a global scale, with researchers investigating and providing insights on pressing

needs and challenges that beset the society. Hence, HEIs and RPOs become prone to Research Security (RS) risks that threaten national security, the ethical conduct of research and fundamental human rights.

With this manuscript the CHANGER consortium³ aims to identify the challenges raised by RS, discuss policy implications, and recommend policy actions aiming to build resilience to RS threats.

2. The Concept of Research Security and What is at Stake

RS is a relatively recent concept with no clear consensus on its definition. Herein, the definition given by the Council of the European Union (EU) has been adopted, according to which RS is *“the anticipation and management of three types of risks: (a) the undesirable transfer of critical knowledge and technology that may affect the EU’s security (e.g. if channelled to military or intelligence purposes in third countries; (b) malign influence on research where research can be instrumentalised by or from third countries in order to inter alia create disinformation or incite self-censorship among students and researchers infringing academic freedom and research integrity; (c) ethical or integrity violations, where knowledge and technologies are used to suppress, infringe on or undermine fundamental values and rights.”*⁵ This definition of RS overlays -to a certain extent- with established concepts in research, such as dual use, misuse, data protection, intellectual property, ethical conduct of research and research integrity.

Why does RS demand policy attention? On one side, inadequate safeguards may expose research to malign influences, misuse, and applications that threaten security, violate human rights, or undermine ethical standards. On the other side, openness and international collaboration that drive scientific progress and innovation must be preserved. The challenge lies in striking a careful balance between protecting research from foreign interference and maintaining collaboration, which essential for a vibrant and globally connected research ecosystem.

3. Methodology

Existing RS initiatives were initially identified from the scientific and grey literature through an integrative review approach.⁴ This was followed by a collaborative study, drawing on collective expertise and utilising the knowledge of the interdisciplinary CHANGER consortium in research ethics, research integrity, human rights and policy advising at various research areas.

4. Existing Initiatives

Despite its recent conceptualization, RS has been swiftly recognized as a critical issue at a global scale, as evidenced by relevant initiatives at the international (Supplementary Table S1), European (Supplementary Table S2) and national (Supplementary Table S3) level, as well as by scientific Societies and Associations (Supplementary Table S4). These initiatives include communications, recommendations, but also regulations which are not specific but relate to RS, such as export control, and screening of foreign direct investments into the EU. Among the various multi-level initiatives reflecting diverse approaches to RS, particular attention should be drawn to the Council Recommendation on Enhancing Research Security (2024)⁵ (Supplementary Table S5) and the Toolkit on Tackling Foreign Interference (2022)⁶

(Supplementary Table S6), because these policy instruments specifically address the issue of RS and offer mitigation strategies aimed at multiple stakeholder groups.

The number of existing initiatives highlights that RS is being recognized as an urgent issue, which needs to be handled at different levels in a complementary way. But it also highlights a difference in the pace of development, adoption and implementation of frameworks between continents but also between European countries. By now, a relevant legislative framework on national security strategy for government-supported research is already in place in the USA; France has a Decree on Protecting the Nation's Scientific and Technical capabilities; the Netherlands have set up a National Contact Point for Knowledge Security; Germany has established a Competence Centre for international academic cooperation (Supplementary Table S3), with other countries in Europe lagging behind in setting up framework components for RS.

5. Learning from Research Ethics and Integrity

Herein, it is argued that Europe needs to take advantage of existing know-how and infrastructures to tackle RS, integrating RS considerations with the existing research culture of ethical conduct of research and research integrity –with the necessary support. Research ethics and integrity infrastructures are composed of diverse but complementary elements, all working in synergy to ensure responsible and ethical research: principles, values, codes of conduct, educational programs, administrative procedures, management mechanisms and coordination structures, as well as relevant policies and legislation at various levels. Although adaptations are necessary to some of the elements of research ethics infrastructures (see CHANGER project³ for changes in the ethics review process), ethics has been an important factor influencing the “epistemic identity” of the EU inducing policies in science and technology,⁷ while ethical principles have been fundamental in promoting an ethical mindset and research integrity for the research community.⁸

Research ethics and integrity are based on values and principles.^{9,10} Ultimately, RS is also about responsible research and ethical behavior aiming to safeguard democratic values and ensure that research is protected from malevolent interference and its outcomes are used for the benefit of society (Figure 1). Research ethics relies on a deep understanding of how critical it is to promote scientific advancements and innovation together with balancing the risks for research participants and their rights, as well as for all members of society, respect of animals and the environment. Similarly, RS is about ensuring that collaborative research and open science are in equipoise with security. Research ethics is based on joint actions of different members of the research ecosystem, without which the balance of scientific progress and protection of human and nature's integrity would not be feasible. Likewise, RS risks to be addressed demand cooperation of all involved parties. Therefore, ethics and integrity¹¹ infrastructures may serve as a setting example of how RS could be addressed at different levels. Critical know-how and experience from ethics and integrity infrastructures can be transferred to RS, either by strengthening existing practices and structures or by developing new ones to support RS.

Figure 1. Empirical similarities and distinctions among research ethics, research integrity and research security.

6. Challenges

The implementation of RS presents a broad array of challenges for HEIs, RPOs and the research community at large. This manuscript focuses specifically on a subset of these challenges, those identified as foundational and most urgent to address, based on their critical intersections with established principles and practices of research ethics and research integrity. These challenges were deliberately selected because they represent essential entry points for policy development.

6.1. Research security understanding varies between members of the research ecosystem

RS remains a relatively nascent concept, and thus, all members of the research ecosystem (e.g. researchers, academics, industry actors, funding bodies, and policymakers) acting at diverse levels do not necessarily have a common, precise and clear understanding of what RS is, the risks involved and their implications. Even among members of the research ethics and research integrity community, who acknowledge values and principles that need to be respected and are familiar with good research practices, the concept of RS may have diverse interpretations, with several questions requiring clarifications such as: a) Does RS apply to communities within physical borders (e.g. a nation or the EU) or those within social borders (e.g. ethnicity) or both? Could protecting from foreign interference overly focus on the former at the expense of the latter? b) At which level should RS risks be assessed and managed, e.g. at the researcher-, project- or community-level and which level policy should be focused on? c) Are risks external e.g. utilisation of research findings by third parties for their own malign purposes, and/or internal e.g. improper leakage of findings by researchers themselves? d) How does RS differ between research and innovation in the public and private sector? e) Most importantly, do existing ethics and integrity infrastructures, as well as existing legislation on data protection, intellectual property, cybersecurity, dual use and misuse suffice to tackle RS risks?

Different terminologies related to RS have been used in various guidance and regulatory documents by different countries and organisations (Supplementary Tables S1-S3): *Foreign interference; Security-relevant research; Risks related to international R&I cooperation; Knowledge security; Responsible internationalization of research; Trusted research; Secure innovation*. Such diversity in terms can cause further ambiguity and misinterpretation of what RS is, can hinder the establishment of a unified framework for discussion and/or action and, result in inconsistencies in the implementation of RS measures by various stakeholders, complicating alignment efforts across nations, regions, organizations, or sectors. At the same time, the concept of RS is not static, and requires to be versatile enough to respond to the changing research environment, the emerging technologies and the increasing geopolitical tensions. These highlight a critical gap in coherence and, therefore, the need for conceptual clarity.

6.2. Balancing institutional autonomy with research security considerations

In order to address and mitigate RS risks, institutions will need to adapt existing policies or develop new ones. This may inadvertently impose significant administrative burden and delays for institutions and, subsequently, for researchers. Such burden could be disproportionate to the scale or nature of research conducted within certain HEIs and RPOs, potentially hindering international collaboration, institutional autonomy, and academic freedom. Paradoxically, delays and complex procedures to prevent and manage RS risks may result in reduced vigilance and oversight during research implementation. Indeed, lessons from the ethical oversight of research teach us the importance of maintaining a balance between procedural shortcomings and maintenance of the highest ethical standards in research.¹² Accordingly, any policies and procedures for RS which will be implemented at the national or institutional level, need to provide sufficient flexibility to HEIs and RPOs, as well as autonomy to tailor their procedures to context-specific research, by leveraging existing infrastructures, rather than imposing uniform requirements horizontally that may exacerbate compliance and procedural challenges.

6.3. Lack of research security expertise

Most HEIs and RPOs are currently in the early steps of engaging with the complex and evolving landscape of RS. As they begin to develop institutional strategies to address RS considerations, these organisations face significant uncertainty. At present, there is limited institutional experience to draw upon, and a notable scarcity of expertise in RS capable of offering informed guidance and practical support. This lack of a well-established knowledge base and expert community hampers the ability of HEIs, RPOs, and individual researchers to proactively identify and manage potential risks. Drawing from experience in research ethics, the role of ethics experts, either as members of institutional Research Ethics Committees (RECs), Framework Programme ethics appraisal scheme experts, Ethics Advisors or Mentors in research projects,¹³ have highlighted the value of having a critical mass of specialised professionals that provide advice and recommendation to researchers, which can be used as a lesson.

6.4. Lack of capacities and tools

At present, there is a remarkable absence of established models or best practices to systematically and effectively integrate RS considerations into the research lifecycle. Researchers across disciplines lack necessary capacities and institutional support to

adequately identify, assess, and mitigate RS-related risks. This capacity gap is further intensified by the unavailability of practical, fit-for-purpose tools for RS risk assessment and management, limiting researchers in addressing the complex RS challenges. The current situation underscores a critical need to actively involve researchers to take RS considerations in the research design with the support from context-specific tools.

Knowledge from the ethics review process, could be helpful for RS in this case. RECs alone cannot ensure the ethical conduct of research in the changing research environment, unless ethical reflections are introduced upstream (i.e. well before finalizing the research design and/or applying for approval to RECs). This presupposes that researchers are actively involved in the ethical design of their own activities. This is the main idea that the CHANGER project represents and supports: to promote ethics-by-design practices in research that foster accountability and responsibility, and to encourage the use of tools which enhance the ethical conduct of research. Under an innovative approach, ethics review experts are expected to act in continued collaboration with researchers, providing advice for ethics compliance throughout the research life-cycle of the research. The need to build analogous reflexivity and capacities for RS considerations in the research community is apparent.

7. Policy Recommendations

Building upon the guidance provided across various levels (Supplementary Tables S1-4), a coherent set of Policy Recommendations is presented herein, aiming to strengthen efforts to tackle RS risks in the short and medium term. In this context, “short term” refers to actions that could be implemented within a period of two years, and “medium term” refers to actions that could be implemented within a period of four years. The proposed Policy Recommendations are informed by insights from the CHANGER project as well as from lessons derived from the frameworks of research ethics and research integrity.

7.1. Establish a common understanding and shared responsibility

A common understanding of RS should be established by: a) using clear definitions and articulations of RS, to promote standardised terminology in all relevant documents, b) developing training material to educate all different members of the research ecosystem on the concept of RS, and provide clarifications on potential (misapprehended) overlaps with other notions, such as dual use, misuse, intellectual property, data protection, cybersecurity etc. (see also policy recommendation 2) and, c) creating channels for stakeholders to provide feedback on their interpretations, enabling iterative refinement of the shared understanding, as new insights, technologies or geopolitical tensions may emerge.

Similarly to the ethical conduct of research which is a collective responsibility of all parties involved, ensuring RS should be conceived as a shared responsibility, merely because risks cannot be addressed unless all parties of the research and innovation ecosystem take joint actions. In order to promote RS as a shared responsibility it is required: a) to identify relevant stakeholders in an inclusive manner (HEIs, RPOs and their researchers both from the public and private sector, national and European research funding agencies, policy makers at the national and European level, scientific associations and bodies, intergovernmental organisations), and identify stakeholders that share not only the same concerns but also the same interests, resulting in alliances among European and non-European actors to design and adopt comprehensive strategies against RS risks, and b) to invite all identified actors to a continuous and versatile dialogue, which will foster communication and support joint actions to effectively tackle the global challenges (Box 1).

Box 1. Challenge and policy recommendation 1.

The EU is invited to establish a common understanding of RS by leveraging the ERA governance structures and the European Centre of Expertise on Research Security to be established at the Union level which is expected to contribute to creating an EU-wide community of practice and maintain a structural dialogue with stakeholder organisations.⁵ HEIs and RPOs are also invited to establish a common understanding of RS and promote RS as a shared responsibility at the institutional level, through appropriate training material/programs at the institutional level (see also Policy Recommendation 2).

7.2. Foster institutional autonomy by leveraging existing procedures

In order to tackle RS risks and at the same time avoid resource-intensive and excessive administrative burden, HEIs and RPOs should use procedures and practices already in place at the institutional level. As a first step, existing training programs on research ethics and research integrity could be utilised and further enriched to include aspects of dual use, export control, misuse, cybersecurity, intellectual property, conflict of interest, and RS aspects such as responsible internationalisation of research, foreign travel security, insider threat awareness and identification, and due diligence, as well as the importance of protecting academic freedom and values. This is particularly critical for institutions dealing with research in novel and disruptive technologies, for which all researchers and staff involved should receive mandatory training not only on research ethics and integrity but also on RS considerations (Box 2). This approach will allow HEIs and RPOs to adopt context-specific training programs, which are tailored to their research activities, and embed RS considerations in the culture of ethical conduct of research and research integrity. Subsequently, HEIs and RPOs can gradually assess whether the establishment of new practices and/or structures, such as institutional RS Committees, are deemed necessary or not to tackle RS risks.

Box 2. Challenge and policy recommendation 2.

HEIs and RPOs are invited to adapt existing resources, such as training programs on research ethics and integrity, in the short term. Additionally, national and European funding organisations are invited to support such educational programmes through funding in the medium term. Some HEIs and RPOs in the USA, Sweden, and Norway, already provide courses

on research ethics including topics of research integrity, conflict of interest, dual use research, misuse of research,¹⁰ but this should be extended particularly to RS considerations in more countries, HEIs and RPOs. The identification of RS risks and their management should be integrated into the “research culture”, where elements of ethical conduct of research and integrity of researchers are complemented by RS aspects.

7.3. Cultivate professional expertise

Developing a robust base of professional expertise in RS is critical to ensure that national authorities, HEI and RPOs have access to reliable, context-specific advice and guidance. The establishment of a dedicated cohort of RS experts will be instrumental in supporting the implementation of effective and proportionate RS mechanisms. Such expertise can be cultivated through targeted capacity building efforts which are essential to bridge current capacity gaps, and should include: a) up-skilling of professionals currently working in adjacent domains such as research ethics, research integrity, (cyber)security, critical knowledge in emerging and disrupting areas, and legal compliance, and b) re-skilling of existing members of the research ecosystem, such as research managers and compliance officers (Box 3).

Box 3. Challenge and policy recommendation 3.

The EU is invited to promote training of experts in the short/medium term, for example through the European Centre of Expertise on Research Security to be established at the Union level, expected to contribute to the creation of an EU-wide community of practice. This community of practice could be further strengthened by the inclusion of expert RS Advisors who have received appropriate training and have acquired the necessary competences to provide their insights and offer evidence-informed policies to countries, HEIs and RPOs.

Policy Recommendations 2 and 3 align with the Council Recommendation to support HEIs and RPOs to develop training programmes for practitioners and new staff members, as well as curricula aimed at training the next generation of security advisors and policy-makers.⁵ We further support this by recommending that existing infrastructures for research ethics and integrity should be utilised to provide such training, and existing programs should be adapted to include RS aspects and the value of safeguarding academic freedom and values.

7.4. Support capacity building

Research funding should be provided to explore innovative approaches that build capacities in researchers and their institutions to address RS challenges, as well as to develop risk assessment tools for RS. As an example, we propose the novel concept of “*research security-by-design*”, which is based on the principle of “*ethics-by-design*” as implemented in the CHANGER project. Research security-by-design is based on the idea that RS risks should be identified and mitigated already from the initial phase of the project design (Box 4). Researchers and RS experts should be engaged in reflection and dialogue during research

design to effectively minimise RS threats in international, complex research projects. It can include certain “checkpoints” implemented into the project design, such as the research domain/technology involved, a plan of international collaborators and their institutional reputation, potential conflicts of interest and conflicts of commitment, plans of which research aspects should be “as open as possible and as closed as necessary”, potential cybersecurity risks etc. Such a procedure ultimately results in capacity building, as it aims particularly to support researchers who have limited prior exposure to aspects of RS, to identify and minimize RS risks in their work. It creates situational awareness for researchers who are called to understand and effectively respond to potential risks of RS in their research. It empowers freedom of scientific research and allows for informed choices that will be implemented in the project design. It recognises the need for adaptations to the severity of security risks for different types of research at different institutions and at different research projects, ensuring institutional autonomy. In order to explore “research security-by-design” or other innovative approaches, appropriate funding is necessary to develop RS risk assessment tools to be used by researchers themselves but also by HEIs and RPOs, as well as to develop benchmarking tools for HEIs and RPOs to assess their capacities for risk identification and management (Box 4). This approach can be enhanced if researchers have received previous training on RS (policy recommendation 2), and if RS has been cultivated as a professional expertise for RS advisors who are able to provide their expert insights (policy recommendation 3).

Box 4. Challenge and policy recommendation 4.

The EU and national funding agencies are invited to embrace this critical Policy Recommendation, that will support research in RS and provide novel tools to manage RS threats. Such initiatives can be covered by existing EU framework programmes and national funds.

Policy Recommendation 4 aligns with the Council Recommendation on enhancing research security, encouraging Member States (MS) to: a) strengthen the evidence base for research security policymaking, through conducting or commissioning policy-relevant research, among others, and b) proactively contribute to the EU’s one-stop-shop platform on tackling R&I foreign interference by sharing tools and resources developed through public funding with the aim to facilitate their cross-border uptake.⁵ The proposed Policy Recommendation of research security-by-design approaches can be an inherent part of RS risk identification and management procedures, as described in various guidance documents including the Toolkit on Tackling Foreign Interference,⁶ the Council Recommendation⁵ and the OECD,¹⁰ while fully respecting academic freedom and institutional autonomy. As a starting point, such an approach can be first explored in research involving emerging and disruptive technologies in the three critical technology areas (AI, Quantum technologies and Biotechnologies), as recognised by the EC.²

8. Why these Policy Recommendations?

The proposed Policy Recommendations can be implemented in short and medium term, without encompassing the creation of new structures, such as new national or institutional RS Committees. The advantage of this approach is two-fold: a) Firstly and most importantly, it cultivates the integration of RS considerations in the existing culture of ethical conduct and integrity in research. This enables all members of the research ecosystem to have direct access to adapted training programmes designed to also raise awareness on RS, fostering a seamless integration of common principles and values, and b) it avoids the imposition of excessive procedural compliance, which could be perceived by researchers as an administrative burden, risking questioning and detraction from understanding the importance of safeguarding RS.

Additionally, these policy recommendations support grassroots initiatives on RS, encouraging dialogue and reflection among researchers. This approach fosters awareness, shared responsibility and a proactive responsiveness to the risks associated with international collaboration, while maintaining freedom of research. Even more importantly, these policy recommendations are instrumental in building capacity for researchers, HEIs and RPOs to address RS challenges effectively. Finally, policy recommendation 4 facilitates context-specific adaptations at the project design phase, enhances researchers' situational awareness, and strengthens both capacity building and sustainability in building resilience to RS risks. By respecting institutional autonomy, it allows researchers and institutions to implement measures proportionate to the specific risks associated with individual research projects, ensuring a balanced and effective approach to address RS risks.

8. Concluding remarks

Leveraging experience and insights from existing research ethics and integrity infrastructure offers valuable opportunities to raise awareness and establish procedures for safeguarding RS in the long term. The proposed policy recommendations should be considered as complementary to existing guidance and policy recommendations. They allow for flexibility in order to meet the specific research needs of each HEI and RPO, and are proportionate to the related risks rising from each research project, respecting the autonomy of HEIs and RPOs and protecting freedom of research, while reaping the benefits of joint collaborations. We propose that by fostering capacity-building for researchers and cultivating a culture of awareness (as in the case of ethics reviews in the changing research environment), shared responsibility, and proactive responsiveness, the responsible internationalization of research can be effectively realized. In this effort, funding agencies, HEIs and RPOs need to act as stewards of secure research, demonstrating commitment to support the research community. This way, RS policies can be recognised as an opportunity to research and development, to protect research outcomes and ensure that they are being used for the benefit of society.

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Declaration of Interests

The authors have nothing to declare.

Supplementary Material

1 **Supplementary Table S1.** An overview of existing initiatives relevant to research security at the international level, in chronological order.

Date, Institution	Initiatives Existing initiatives relevant to Research Security at the international level
2021, OECD	Report on Integrity and Security in The Global Research Ecosystem by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), which analyses publicly available documents and additional information collected from a group of 13 OECD countries represented on an expert group and includes the outcomes of two dedicated international workshops. The report identifies and analyses good practices to safeguard national and economic security whilst protecting freedom of enquiry, promoting international research cooperation, and ensuring openness and non-discrimination.
06/2022 and 05/2023, G7	Paper by the G7 on Common Values and Principles on RS and Research Integrity (2022). Best Practices for Secure and Open Research (2023) by the G7 Working Group on the Security and Integrity of the Global Research Ecosystem (G7 SIGRE WG), setting the G7 common values and best practices of research integrity and RS: i) to establish resources to promote awareness and forums for dialogue and information sharing on RS and integrity across all research stakeholders, ii) to Identify areas of risk activity by conducting due diligence and ensuring transparency and the disclosure of relevant information, and, iii) to implement risk mitigation measures, both as standard organizational practice and for individual research projects.
06/2022, OECD	Report on Integrity and Security in the Global Research Ecosystem by the Organisation for Economic Co-ordination and Development (OECD), which identifies security risks arising from the internationalisation of research and analyzes good practices to safeguard national and economic security whilst protecting freedom of enquiry, promoting international research cooperation, and ensuring openness and non-discrimination. The report stresses that RS calls for the adoption of various measures (e.g. legislation, awareness raising activity, capacity building) and multilevel coordination.

2 RS: research security.

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5 **Supplementary Table S2.** An overview of existing initiatives relevant to research security at the European level, in chronological order.

Date, Institution	Initiatives relevant to Research Security at the European level
19/03/2019, EU	Regulation (EU) 2019/452 on establishing a framework for the screening of foreign direct investments into the Union, which lays down rules to check such investment on the grounds of security and public order.
18/05/2018, EC	Communication COM/2021/252 on the Global Approach to R&I Europe's strategy for international cooperation in a changing world, stating the intention to pursue reciprocal openness in R&I and provide for an investment strategy based on a differentiated approach, to ensure an international playing field that is as open as possible and as closed as necessary.
20/05/2021, EU	Regulation (EU) 2021/821 setting up a Union regime for the control of exports, brokering, technical assistance, transit and transfer of dual-use items designed to avoid unlawful dissemination of EU knowledge, technology, and know-how that qualify as dual-use items or associated technical assistance.
28/04/2021, EU	Regulation (EU) 2021/695 laying down the rules for participating in the EU's funding programme for R&I Horizon Europe, including all entities regardless of their jurisdiction, including also new obligations intended to safeguard research security through reciprocity.
19/09/2021, EC	Recommendation (EU) 2021/1700 on internal compliance programmes for controls of research involving dual-use items under Regulation (EU) 2021/821 for the control of exports, brokering, technical assistance, transit and transfer of dual-use items, which provides MS and exporters, including research organisations and researchers, guidance to fulfil their obligations.
17/01/2022, EC	Staff Working Document on tackling foreign interference adopted by the EC. It is intended as a toolkit of measures developed by the EC and MS to mitigate foreign interference in research and innovation, it outlines best practices to support EU HEIs and RPOs in safeguarding their fundamental values, including academic freedom, integrity and institutional autonomy, as well as to protect their staff, students, research findings and assets.
08/03/2022, EU	Marseille Declaration on International Cooperation in Research and Innovation (R&I), in which EU ministers for higher education, research, and innovation agree to promote and protect freedom of scientific research and academic freedom in international research, innovation, and higher education collaboration while taking measures to counter and manage security risks inherent to international cooperation.
09/03/2022, European Parliament	Resolution P9_TA(2022)0064 on foreign interference in all democratic processes in the EU, including disinformation, in which the Parliament recognized that foreign interference constitutes a serious violation of the universal values and principles on which the Union is founded and the need for a coordinated strategy against foreign interference.
06/04/2022, European Parliament	Resolution P9_TA(2022)0112 on a global approach to R&I: Europe's strategy for international cooperation in a changing world, in which the Parliament supported the principle of enabling reciprocal access to research programmes, open science and intellectual property protection while requiring partners to respect and match European standards for the protection of intellectual property, welcoming the EC's toolkit on Tackling Foreign Interference.
10/06/2022, Council of Europe	Council's Conclusions on principles and values for international cooperation in R&I, setting out the values and principles which must guide international cooperation in research and innovation and recommends mitigation measures to avoid foreign interference and manage the risks inherent in international R&I cooperation, including safeguards of intellectual and industrial property rights, and personal data.
02/12/2022, Council of Europe	Council's Conclusions on research infrastructure, in which the EC was invited to present a revised European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures by the end of 2023 in view of the evolving European RI ecosystem and landscape of RI facilities, which accommodate their user strategies and access policies for operations under various business models, serve users in the physical, remote and virtual access modes via secure connectivity.

01/03/2023, EC	Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/499 on a Code of Practice on the management of intellectual assets for knowledge valorisation in the ERA, recommending strategic intellectual assets management practices to enable open science, open innovation and training for universities and other public research organisations on intellectual assets management, including in joint R&I activities.
09/05/2023, European Parliament	Parliament's resolution C/2023/1059 (P9_TA(2023)0131) on critical technologies for security and defence: state of play and future challenges highlighted the growing relevance of research security, in which the Parliament called the EC to better connect EU civil, defence and security programmes and instruments with the relevant stakeholders, in particular in the field of innovation, making clear that RS is expected to become more central to EU R&I programming and implementation.
23/05/2023, Council of Europe	The Presidency Note for the exchange of views on knowledge security and responsible internationalization, acknowledges that threats from foreign states and non-state actors can lead to unwanted knowledge transfer and interference in R&I activities, that security risks threaten to seriously damage the international research ecosystem, stressing the need to ensure complementarity between openness and security with respect to ethics, fundamental rights and academic freedom.
20/06/2023, EU	Joint communication JOIN(2023) 20 by the European Parliament, European Council, Council on “European Economic Security Strategy” on setting the priorities of an EU Economic Security Strategy by promoting our own competitiveness, protecting ourselves from economic security risks, and partnering with the broadest possible range of countries who share our concerns or interests on economic security.
12/12/2023, EC	Proposal for a Directive on establishing harmonised requirements in the internal market on transparency of interest representation carried out on behalf of third countries, recognizing the opportunity for third-country actors to evade transparency requirements and covertly influence decision-making and democratic processes in the Union and the need for new rules to address foreign influence, including by imposing general obligations on entities receiving foreign funding that would in practice apply to the provision of interest representation on behalf of third countries.
2023-2024, EC	Mutual Learning Exercises on Knowledge Valorisation - Focus on Skills, Intersectoral Cooperation and Incentive Systems with the participation of 12 MS, including an exercise on identifying foreign interference threats and mitigation measures.
17/01/2024, European Parliament	Resolution P9_TA(2024)0022 on promotion of the freedom of scientific research in the EU, presenting views on how to balance the safeguard of RS with the freedom of scientific research, and requests the EC to submit a proposal for an act on the freedom of scientific research including security-associated restrictions.
21/01/2024, EC	Proposal for a Council Recommendation (COM/2024/26) on enhancing RS, adopted on 14 May 2024 (See Council Recommendation 9097/1/24).
24/01/2024, EC	White paper on options for enhancing support for research and development involving technologies with dual-use potential, which launches a broad public consultation of MS, the European Parliament, stakeholders and civil society, and reviews the current relevant EU funding programmes and assesses whether this support is still adequate and strategic in the face of existing and emerging geopolitical challenges outlined in the European Economic Security Strategy, suggesting options for the future. The received input will contribute to the preparation of the next Framework Programme for R&I.
14/05/2024, Council of Europe	Council Recommendation (9097/1/24) on enhancing RS, in which RS is defined based on the risks that need to be avoided and managed. The recommendation invites MS and the EC to take into account specific principles for responsible internationalisation when designing and implementing policy actions to enhance RS, and MS to develop and implement a coherent set of policy actions to enhance RS, while engaging in dialogue with the R&I sector with a view to defining responsibilities and roles and developing a national approach. MS are expected to prepare an action plan to implement it.

6 RS: research security; EU: European Union; EC: European Commission; R&I: research & innovation; MS: member states.

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8 **Supplementary Table S3.** An overview of existing initiatives relevant to research security at the national level, in chronological order.

Date, Institution	Initiatives Existing initiatives relevant to Research Security at the national level
2019, Germany	<p>Competence Centre for International Academic Cooperation by the German Academic Exchange, providing guidance to German higher education and academic institutions to carry out international cooperation activities while ensuring RS and research integrity.</p>
2021, France	<p>A Decree on Protecting the Nation's Scientific and Technical capabilities by the government to protect the most "sensitive" knowledge, expertise and technologies of public and private establishments (research laboratories, companies, etc.) located on national territory that could harm the economic interests of the nation, strengthen foreign military arsenals or weaken French defense capabilities, contribute to the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction and their delivery systems, and be used for terrorist purposes on national territory or abroad. It introduces a label for sensitive scientific infrastructure, both private and public, designated as 'restricted regime zones'.</p>
2013, UK	<p>The Academic Technology Approval Scheme (ATAS) applies to all international students and researchers who are subject to UK immigration control and are intending to study or research at postgraduate level in certain sensitive subjects and research areas, where knowledge could be used in programmes to develop Advanced Conventional Military Technology, weapons of mass destruction or their means of delivery. Researchers and students in these sensitive subjects must apply for an Academic Technology Approval Scheme (ATAS) certificate before they can study or start research in the UK.</p>
2021, UK	<p>Trusted Research and Innovation (TR&I) work programme established by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), in response to the increasing need across the sector to help manage and provide guidance and support in ensuring collaborative activities are done safely and securely and minimise the risks associated with operating within a global research and innovation ecosystem while maximising the opportunities.</p> <p>The UK National Security and Investment Act (2021) provides the government with powers to scrutinise and intervene in business transactions (including by higher education and research organisations) in 17 key areas of the economy, to protect national security. Any R&I activities that UKRI funds within these areas will be subject to enhanced due diligence processes to ensure that risks associated with trusted R&I are effectively identified and proportionately mitigated against.</p> <p>Guidance on Trusted Research for Academia and on Trusted Research for Industry issued by the National Protective Security Authority (NPSA), to help stakeholders to identify risks, and protect research.</p> <p>Guidance on Secure Innovation: guidance for emerging technology sector, issued by the NPSA, to help protect UK companies' technology, reputation, and future success.</p> <p>A Research Collaboration Advice Team (RCAT) established by the Government to offer researchers advice on how to protect their work from hostile activity, to ensure international collaboration is done safely and securely and promote government advice on security-related topics, such as export controls, cyber security and protection of intellectual property.</p>
2022, Netherlands	<p>A National Contact Point for Knowledge Security by different Dutch ministries, which offers help to anyone connected to a knowledge institution with questions about opportunities, risks and practical matters concerning international cooperation.</p>

	National knowledge security guidelines presenting values, risk assessment and management for knowledge security intended to be used to build security awareness and resilience against knowledge security risks faced by Dutch universities, research institutes and universities of applied sciences.
2018, USA	An initiative by the US Department of Justice, focused on specific threats to national security, including educating colleges and universities about potential threats to academic freedom and open discourse from influence efforts on campus.
2021, USA	Presidential Memorandum on Supported Research and Development National Security Policy (NSPM-33) issued by the government, to strengthen protections of US Government-supported research and development against foreign interference and exploitation, and strengthen cooperation between law enforcement agencies and funding agencies. Guidance by the government for Implementing National Security Presidential Memorandum 33 (NSPM-33) on National Security Strategy for US Government-supported Research and Development, including guidance on disclosure policy, oversight and enforcement and, RS programs. The Subcommittee on RS and the Joint Committee on the Research Environment of the National Science & Technology Council issued Recommended Practices for Strengthening the Security and Integrity of America's Science and Technology Research Enterprise for research organisations to protect security and integrity, which include organisational policies and training to researchers on responsible conduct of research.
2023, USA	The Chips and Science Act (H.R.4346) (Sec. 10114) according to which the Department of Energy shall develop and maintain tools and processes to manage and mitigate RS risks, such as a science and technology risk matrix, informed by threats identified by the Office of Intelligence and Counterintelligence, to facilitate determinations of the risk of loss of US intellectual property or threat to the national security of the US. A Congressional Research Service Report highlighting federal and legislative efforts to develop a comprehensive research security strategy, and charging the Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) with a leading role in ensuring that policies and requirements related to RS practices are developed and implemented consistently across the federal government.
2023, Canada	National Security Guidelines for Research Partnerships issued by the Ministry of Innovation, Science and Economic Canada, that integrate national security considerations into the development, evaluation, and funding of research partnerships to help safeguard Canada's research ecosystem from foreign interference, espionage, and unwanted knowledge transfer. Individual researchers are requested to assess the potential national security risks of international collaborative projects. Researchers must complete a risk assessment form when submitting applications for funding.
2019, Australia	Establishment of the University Foreign Interference Taskforce (UFIT) by the Australian Minister for Education, which brings together the university sector and Australian Government agencies to collaboratively support and build an environment of trust and resilience, and to guide a university's decision-making based on proportionate risks.
2021, Australia	Guidelines to Counter Foreign Interference in the Australian University Sector, issued by the University Foreign Interference Taskforce (UFIT) to help manage and engage with risk to deepen resilience against foreign interference in the university sector, to build on risk management policies and security practices already implemented and, assist decision makers to assess the risks from foreign interference. Guidelines include knowledge sharing, due diligence, risk assessment, risk management, and, cybersecurity.

New Zealand [Guidance](#) for Institutions and Researchers on Trusted Research issued by the government, to promote risk identification and measures for research protection.

9 RS: research security.

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11 **Supplementary Table S4.** An overview of existing initiatives relevant to research security by Associations, Societies and Academies, in chronological order.

Date, Institution	Initiatives Existing initiatives relevant to Research Security by Associations, Societies and Academies
2014, Germany	Guidelines by the German Research Foundation (DFG) and the National Academy of Sciences Leopoldina for Handling Security-relevant Research, to minimise risks of misuse and assist self-regulation by individual researchers, research institutions and universities.
12/2019, Canada	Guide on Mitigating Economic and/or Geopolitical Risks in Sensitive Research Projects by the U15 Group of Canadian Research Universities, providing advice and best practices to undertake an economic and geopolitical risk assessment and mitigate key risks, containing practical checklists and a matrix to assess economic and geopolitical risks.
05/2020, APLU, AAU	Briefing on University Actions to Address Concerns about Security Threats and Undue Foreign Government Influence on Campus, by the Association of Public Land-grant Universities (APLU) and the Association of American Universities (AAU). It presents surveyed practices and measures employed by universities to ensure RS, focusing on increased training for researchers, enhanced scrutiny of foreign partnerships, and reviews of international contracts, and calls on the US government to minimise administrative barriers to the establishment of both informal collaborations and formal agreements with international researchers.
2022, Germany	Guidelines by the Max Planck Society for its researchers to identify, assess and mitigate risks relating to human rights, academic freedom, and scientific espionage before they start international collaboration. Administrative headquarters need to approve third-party funds before researchers can accept such funds.
2021, VSNU	Framework on Knowledge Security Dutch Universities, by the Association of Universities in the Netherlands (VSNU), providing guidelines to enable institutions to make well-informed and substantiated decisions about international collaborations and answers the call from government and society to take responsibility as a sector for safeguarding knowledge security.
12/2023, EUA	Policy paper by the European University Association (EUA) where they welcome the emphasis on support for developing and strengthening risk management within universities and other higher education and research-performing institutions, stressing that openness should be responsible, with proportional measures to counter risks.
03/01/2024, EARTO	Position paper by the European Association of Research and Technology Organisations (EARTO), proposing guiding principles for RS and recommending initiatives at EU level to raise awareness of the EU RI community, to comprehensively review practices in Horizon Europe projects, to develop a voluntary training programme leading to certification, and support the creation of secure national and EU platforms for exchange of best practices.
01/2024, LERU	Statement by the League of European Research-intensive Universities (LERU) expressing delight at the Proposal for a Council Recommendation on Enhancing RS, and stresses that academic institutions will need to rely on advice and guidance from a wide range of national and EU authorities to perform their due diligence on RS.
11/2023 and 02/2024, Guild	Statement on Responsible Internationalisation by the Guild of European Research-intensive Universities, stressing the importance of academic freedom and institutional autonomy and that any work between governments and universities to create a culture of responsibility about international collaboration must be supported by transparent, up-to-date, and accurate information about which actors are of concern, and why. Following the Proposal for a Council Recommendation on enhancing research security, a Statement by the Guild welcomed the opportunity to co-develop Europe's approach to RS and highlighted the need for investment by MS to achieve the right degree of capacity building across R&I organisations.

12 RS: research security; R&I: research & innovation.

Supplementary Table S5. An overview of the Council Recommendation on enhancing research security.³

Stakeholders	Recommendations on enhancing Research Security
MS	<p>Collaboration (national-international level):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dialogue with the R&I sector 2. A national approach (guidelines, measures, other initiatives) 3. Information exchange (between RPOs & RFOs) 4. Engage with the private sector (research-intensive start-ups, spin offs, SMEs) 5. Cross-sectoral cooperation (within government) 6. Application of the recommendation's measures to international cooperation activities (related to researchers' mobility) 7. International cooperation (involving critical knowledge & technology) <p>Policy actions/support measures:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Policy actions to foster RS 9. A support structure/service to deal with risks of international cooperation 10. Compliance with the applicable Union export control rules for dual-use items, national measures on intangible technology transfer, implementation/ enforcement of restrictive measures <p>Instruments:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. Evidence base for RS policymaking (threat landscape analysis) 12. Resilience testing and incident simulations (considering support of the EC) 13. Proactively contribute to the Union's one-stop-shop platform on tackling research and innovation foreign interference (sharing tools, resources)
RFOs	<p>Risk-appraisal, safeguarding measures, assurance for high -risk projects:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. RS as an integral part of the application process to identify up-front potential risks and threats 2. A risk-appraisal for research projects that raise concerns proportionate to their risk profile 3. Consider risks related to international cooperation (research partnership agreements), include key framework conditions (e.g. values, fundamental rights) 4. Relevant Union funding programmes to be considered when applying safeguarding measures in national funding programmes 5. Applicants seek assurance from prospective partners for high-risk profile projects
RPOs	<p>Collaboration:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Information exchange, peer learning, development of tools and guidelines, incident reporting among peers <p>Risk-appraisal/management:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Internal risk management procedures (risk appraisal, due diligence on prospective partners etc.) 3. Consider possible risks related to the international cooperation and include key framework conditions 4. Assess risks related to foreign government-sponsored talent programmes (undesirable obligations) <p>Capacity building:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Invest in dedicated in-house RS expertise and skills, assign RS responsibility at appropriate levels, invest in cyber hygiene and in a culture in which openness and security are in balance
EC	<p>Coordination/collaboration:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open Method of Coordination, ERA governance structures, support the implementation of this recommendation (awareness, peer learning, capacity building, consistency of policies) 2. Engage with the R&I sector and MS to increase transparency of research funding sources and affiliations of researchers 3. Dialogue & cooperation with international partners (exchange information, experience, best practices) <p>Research supporting infrastructure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. A Union one-stop-shop platform (on tackling R&I foreign interference to consolidate data, tools, reports, resources) <p>Policy actions/Support measures:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Policy making evidence, MS expertise, a European center of expertise on RS linking it to the one-stop-shop platform 6. Enhance situational awareness among policymakers (assessing hybrid threats) 7. A resilience testing methodology for RPOs (on a voluntary basis for MS) 8. A biennial flagship event on RS (sharing information and solution-oriented exchanges) 9. Guidance on risk appraisal procedures and on the application of relevant Union legislation

MS: Member States; RFOs: Research Funding Organisations; RPOs: Research Performing Organisations; EC: European Commission; R&I: Research & Innovation; SMEs: Small and Medium Enterprises; ERA: European Research Area.

Supplementary Table S6. An overview of the mitigation measures described in the EC Toolkit on Tackling R&I Foreign Interference.⁶

Area	Mitigation measures for tackling R&I foreign interference
Values	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify countries and partner institutions where academic freedom is at risk 2. Conduct a vulnerability assessment to understand external pressures on academic freedom and integrity in your institution 3. Strengthen commitment to academic freedom and integrity at institutional and individual levels 4. Continue to cooperate with partners in repressive settings
Governance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Publish a Code of Conduct for Foreign Interference 2. Establish a Foreign Interference Committee
Partnerships	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop general prerequisites for the implementation of a risk management system 2. Establish a sound procedure for developing robust partnership agreements
Cybersecurity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Raise awareness of cybersecurity risks 2. Detect and prevent cybersecurity attacks from foreign interference actors 3. Respond to and recover from cybersecurity attacks from foreign interference